

Human and Financial Resource Management: Tools for Effective Implementation of Entrepreneurship Education in Universities in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Entrepreneurship education is one aspect of Nigeria education system that is expected to make the citizens live a functional and fulfilling life after graduation. This paper is on human and financial resource management: tools for effective implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities in Nigeria. The paper looked at the general concept of entrepreneurship education, its importance to both students and the society. The objectives of entrepreneurship education as enshrined in the national policy on education (2013) were highlighted, the concept of human and material resources were also discussed. The paper discussed in details two key areas such as; influence of human resources management on the implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities in Nigeria and influence of financial resource management on the implementation of entrepreneurship education in universities in Nigeria. The paper concluded that the presence of human resources alone cannot make entrepreneurship education a success; relevant financial resources are much needed to compliment the human resources. Therefore, the provision of both categories of resources in our universities in the right quality and quantity will make the required difference in terms of implementation. It was recommended that; all the stakeholders concerned with the implementation of entrepreneurship education should work relentlessly and collaboratively to ensure that the right thing is done in terms of proper provision of human and financial resources for the programme and there should be regular review of the existing material resources for entrepreneurship education in terms of relevance in line with the dynamics of change ant time.

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Introduction

In Nigeria today, school leavers including university graduates in their millions, roam the streets searching for non-existing collar jobs. It has become increasingly difficult for school leavers from all levels and types of education (including vocational/technical/business education graduates) to transit from school to wage earning employment as hundreds of thousands of them are turned into the labour market at the end of every academic session; without a corresponding rise in paid jobs. Employers of labour (private and public), now shortlist only first class and second class (upper) honours degree graduates for possible employment. Only a handful of Nigerian graduates fall into these two categories. There is thus, a high rate of unemployment which keeps mounting as more students graduate (Duze, 2010)

Entrepreneurship education is therefore one aspect of Nigeria education system that is expected to make the citizens live a functional and fulfilling life after graduation. However, Nigeria doesn't seem to be getting it right. A major defect in the Nigerian educational system, inclusive of the universities, is its theoretical inclination. For one instance, most Nigerian universities produce graduate who are at best only suited for white collar jobs and have little or no basic skills of any other vocational relevance. Naturally, such a situation will lead to high unemployment rate especially among university graduates (Ejere & Tende, 2012).

The Nigerian government in her effort to ensure job opportunities for students after graduating from the universities established a compulsory entrepreneurship education course. Entrepreneurship is no doubt a dynamic process of vision, change, and creation. It requires an application of energy and passion towards the creation and implementation of new ideas and creative solutions. In view of the positive social and economic effects of entrepreneurship, many Nigerian universities are advancing entrepreneurial thinking and behaviour to develop students' awareness of the relevance of entrepreneurship training. Okojie (as cited in Okonkwo, 2013) affirmed that Nigerian educational programmes lay much emphasis on theories rather than the combination of theories and practical. Hence, it is hoped that government should encourage diversification of economy through adequate support for private establishment and practical acquisition of skill such as entrepreneurship education programmes in higher institutions.

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United Nation Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO] (2020) stated that entrepreneurship education is made up of all kinds of experiences that give students the ability and vision of how to access and transform opportunities of different kinds. With this knowledge, students can set up small business enterprise rather than remain jobless for a long period after graduation. This reflect in Nigerian's National Policy on Education which states that education is the most reliable instrument for propelling change, as no fundamental change can occur in any society except through educational/evolution that impact on the intellect (Federal Government of Nigeria [FRN], 2013).

The entrepreneurship education delivered to undergraduates at 200 levels seems not to be meeting the objectives for the unavoidable course as a general studies course. The content delivery and management of the course seems to be porous. There is sky-scraping failure rate and many students struggle for a minimum pass mark of 40%. Despite the fact that this laudable course of entrepreneurship education programme has been mounted in the universities for job creation and skills acquisition, the problem of unemployment is still ravaging the society. Several challenges currently face Nigerian universities in their bid to properly entrench entrepreneurship education as important curriculum issue across all disciplines. Lack of lecturers with practical entrepreneurial training and consciousness, majority of lecturers still do not know enough the aims, contents and work method of entrepreneurship education

Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship education is a type of learning that equips individuals with the knowledge, skills, and mindset necessary to start and manage their own businesses or ventures. It typically covers topics like business planning, marketing, finance, and leadership. Entrepreneurship education can be offered in various settings, including schools, universities, and specialized programs or workshops. It aims to foster creativity, innovation, and the ability to identify and pursue business opportunities. This education is valuable for aspiring entrepreneurs and can also benefit individuals in various career paths by enhancing their problem-solving and critical thinking skills. Fang et al. (2015) asserted that entrepreneurship education is the process of

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providing individuals with the ability to recognized commercial opportunities and the knowledge, skills and attitudes to act on them. Entrepreneurship education was introduced at tertiary level of education with the aims of making students acquire specific skills notwithstanding their area of study. In some institutions, they are introduced at 200 and 300 levels as General Studies Course (GST). The National University Commission (NUC) through the presidency in 2006 directed that entrepreneurship education be obligatory for every university student for at least two semesters in course-of-diversity career. The NUC further directed the full take off of the programme for all the universities to be completed by 2007/2008. The NUC further calls for list of problems so far encountered in the running of the programme to be forwarded on or before one week of receipt of the letter.

The National Universities Commission (NUC) Act No. 48, 1988 empowers the commission to lay down minimum standard for all programme taught in Nigerian Universities (Audretsch et al., 2016). In 2001 a benchmark was established for each programme in all the discipline taught in Nigerian Universities (Falck et al., 2016). In the area of entrepreneurship education the benchmark are as follows:

1. Building Construction: Construction of a separate building block or renovation of existing ones that will accommodate at least 50 students and personnel at a given time.
2. Equipment: The centre should be equipped to standard that will make training more meaningful,
3. Budget; Allocation for running the centers.

Bacigalupo et al. (2016) further enumerated the aims of entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions as follows:

1. Providing meaningful education to the youth to be self-employed and self-reliant.
2. Providing graduate with enough skills that will make them to be creative and innovative in identifying new business opportunities.
3. Providing graduates with enough training in risk management, to make uncertainty bearing more possible and easy to give young graduates training to establish a career in small and medium scale business etc.

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The effective implementation of this course in universities in the Nigeria requires human, material resources and financial resources. A resource can be defined as a useful or valuable possession or means of support for man in making a living. Resources in the universities for entrepreneurship education consist of human resources, material resources and financial resources. Human resources consist of lecturers, ancillary staff, their preparations, upgrading, motivation and professional commitment. At the center of implementation of entrepreneurship education are the lecturers, their quality and quantity are crucial to the achievement of the programme. In supporting this assertion, the researcher agreed with the opinions of Fang et al. (2018) that without competent teaching staff and adequate material resources, a well-funded functional education system will fall below expectation

Importance of Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship transcends skill acquisition. It is the acquisition of necessary skills matched with innovativeness, creativity, boldness, confidence, drive, energy, and courage to be able to create employment for self and for others. It involves exploring, analyzing, evaluating, exploiting business opportunities and rigorously pursuing such opportunities to a successful end which eventually culminates in the opening of a business enterprise.

UNESCO (2020) emphasized that the purposes of Entrepreneurship education to include the following;

1. Educating individuals for and about business,
2. Providing a continuous programme of planned learning experience designed to equip individuals to fulfill effectively three roles.
3. Providing and distributing goods and services as workers,
4. Using the product as consumers, and making wise socio-economic decision.

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Human resource constitutes a vital vein of any institution. The human resource in the school system include: teachers, support staff in the school, students, parents, community members and a host of other interest and social group. Oluwasuen (2016) defined human resource management as the planning, organizing, coordinating, controlling, manipulating and maintaining all personnel and stakeholders in education. Human resource is responsible for the management of other resources in the school. Human resources in the school are managed through recruitment, promotion, descriptive staff development, environment, evaluation, welfare services, transfer of staff, orientation and so on. Hassan (2013) viewed human resource management as that part of management process that specializes in the management of people in work organizations. They maintained that human resource management emphasizes that employees are critical to achieving sustainable competitive advantage, that human resource practices need to be integrated with the corporate strategy, and that human resource specialists help organizational controllers to meet both efficiency and equity objectives especially in implementing entrepreneurship education. According to Owan (2018), all activities of any institution are initiated by the persons that make up that institution. Plant, offices, computer, automated equipment and all inputs that the school uses are unproductive except for the human effort and direction. Human resource could be efficient, effective, and adequately utilized and managed if financial resources are adequately provided.

School finance is an aspect of school management. It is concerned with revenue allocation, disbursement of funds through budget allocation and alternative income into the school. School finance according to Mgbodile (2014) is a broad involving field encompassing three resource-related functions – revenue generation, resources allocation and resource utilization; all aimed at providing educational opportunities and producing educational outcome. School financial resources management covers such areas as the procurement of funds, their allocation, monitoring their use in the interest of accountability and producing report for the relevant stakeholders. Financial resource management is critical to effective management of university education in Nigeria (Onafadeji et al., 2017). Kelvin (2016) described financial resource management as the sum of money that has been set aside for a specific purpose. Financial resource can take any of the

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following forms: physical cash, credit facilities such as trade credits or bank credits, allowances or discount received, and various expenses such as differential expenses like taxes, rent, bills, undistributed profit in the form of retained earnings, receive, and so on (Kaur, 2012). Financial management ensures prudence in the use of school funds to procure facilities necessary for effective implementation of entrepreneurship education in Nigerian universities.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for the study is anchored on Resource Dependence Theory (RDT). Resource Dependence Theory is a social theory that was developed by Pfeffer and Salancik in 1978. It focuses on how organizations, such as schools, rely on external resources to function effectively. Pfeffer and Salancik postulates that organizations often face a scarcity of critical resources like funding, information, and support. These resources are essential for an organization's survival and success. RDT posits that organizations are dependent on external entities such as government agencies, donors, and other organizations to obtain these vital resources they need to operate. The degree of dependence varies according to Pfeffer and Salancik on the resource and the organization's ability to influence the resource providers. RDT emphasizes that an organization's survival and success depend on its ability to manage and influence these resource providers. The theory maintains that organizations employ strategies to reduce their vulnerability to resource providers. These strategies can include diversifying funding sources, forming strategic alliances, and exerting influence over resource providers.

Resource Dependence Theory provides a lens through which researchers can analyze how universities manage and are influenced by their dependence on human and financial resources in the context of entrepreneurship education implementation. It emphasize that universities often need external funding and expertise to establish and sustain entrepreneurship education initiatives. Universities must also attract and retain qualified faculty and staff with expertise in entrepreneurship and must actively seek financial resources, such as grants, donations, or partnerships, to support these programs. The theory relates to this study by emphasizing how the

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availability and management of human and financial resources can significantly impact the successful implementation of such programmes.

Human Resource Management: A tool for effective Implementation of Entrepreneurship Education in Universities in Nigeria

Many Nigerians are facing distressing situation because a lot of money has been supposedly pumped into the universities but no adequate result to show for it. The expectations of all stakeholders is that the university recipients are to be job creators, employers, contributors, but contrary to these expectations, employers employ graduates from the university only to retrain them because of the deficiency in their performance at work. No educational system rises above the quality of her teachers anywhere in the world. Thus the growth and development of skill-based courses in any country of the world largely depend on the quality and adequacy of teachers in these areas of professional endeavour. The bedrock of adequate foundation and training of needed manpower in a country irrespective of area of specialization is a function of the sound products from the teacher education in that country (Ikoro, 2012). According to Uhl-Bien and Arena (2017) the essence of entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions is graduate empowerment, irrespective of their discipline with skills that will offer them the opportunity to engage in income yielding business, whether they are able or not able to secure paid employment in any organization. In consonance with the above assertion, Lyons (2012) summarized the aim of entrepreneurship education by stating that it turns a graduate from being a job seeker to job creator

The education staff includes: teachers, school leaders, support staff, educational administrators hired at different levels of the school system ensure a broad range of functions and bring different types of expertise. Human resources account for a very large proportion of educational expenditure. Over 62% of current expenditure on education is devoted to compensating teachers and 16% to compensating other staff (OECD, 2012). The human resources that are needed to execute entrepreneurship education needed to be properly managed by the institution. Human Resource Management refers to the recruitment, deployment, training, transfer, safety and retirement of employees from a school system. It is concerned with people at work and their relationships within the school system. Human resource management aims to

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achieve both efficiency and justice in the school system. It enables each employee to make his best contributions to success of the school. It seeks to provide fair terms and conditions of employment and thus enables employees to experience job satisfaction.

The goals of entrepreneurship education can be accomplished through the coordinated efforts of all the stakeholders. School managers are therefore, most likely to be judged not just on their own performances, but also on the results achieved by their subordinates. Therefore, effectiveness of educational administrators in the management of human resources in the teaching and learning of entrepreneurship skills may be assessed by such factors as: The strength of motivation and morale of staff and students, the success of their training and development, and the creation of a school environment in which staff and students work willingly and effectively

Financial Resource Mnagement: A tool for effective Implementation of Entrepreneurship Education in Universities in Nigeria

The major purpose of skill- based courses is to develop skilled manpower for self-sustenance, reliance, community and national development. In other words, when an individual is skilled, he is useful to himself and the society he belongs and this will extend to the larger society. The key word here is “skill”. For the students to acquire the desired skills to be able to function effectively, the necessary gadgets are needed to be supplied to the teacher to teach these students. The sustenance of entrepreneurship education depends largely on adequate provision of financial resources for the provision and acquisition of physical and material resources in the schools. Such physical facilities include spacious and well ventilated classrooms, adequately equipped laboratories and technical workshops, well-stocked libraries, assembly halls, recreational ground, farm land, gymnasias, health centers, counseling rooms, staff offices and conveniently placed urinals and latrines. These resources therefore made up of items of furniture, laboratory materials (consumable and non-consumable), motor vehicles, instructional tools, books and other stationery items as well as utilities such as electric power, gas and potable water in the schools.

Financial resources are the funds required for the smooth operations of a school and are regarded as the life-wire of any organization. It is no doubt a more vital instrument with which other factors of administrations are created, maintained, and sustained. In administration of

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universities, funds are essential for the procurement of facilities, equipment, electronics, and communication gadget needed for effective performance of human resources. Outside this, funds are needed to train/develop staff, pay salaries of administrative, academic and non-academic staff. Adequate financial allocation for school administration would go a long way in enhancing goals attainment, as well as their sustainability. Plan and policy implementation are responsive to funds availability. Funds are needed for the acquisition of fixed and current assets and in settling current liabilities and expenditures incurred in the course of administration.

The issue of financial management is a very crucial one and demands serious attention. The role of the school head as a financial manager includes organizing the school business, preparing the school budget, administering capital outlay and debt services, administering school purchase, accounting for school monies and property, providing for a system of internal accounting (Ezeugbor et al., 2016). Further, the administrators' role as a financial managers as enumerated by Okonkwo (2013), include: prepare the school budget; provide for system for internal accounting; administer school purchase; account for school monies; account for school properties; and keep the school office running smoothly. Information on cost of managing facility resources; including equipment, financial issues, such as budgeting, taxes, fees and charges, and donations must be provided. Uchendu et al. (2013) maintained that financial resource management covers such areas as the procurement of funds, their allocation, monitoring their use in the interest of accountability and producing financial reports for the relevant stakeholders. Uchendu et al. further stated that effective financial management ensures that:

- i. all financial regulations and procedures and complied with;
- ii. adequate controls are in place to ensure that expenditures do not exceed income; an
- iii. only authorized expenditures are incurred.

Financial management, however, is an integral part of the responsibility of an education manager because, without good financial management practices, school would find it difficult to achieve their goals. Owan (2018) observed that the main purpose of financial management, be it in government, business or school is the raising of funds and ensuring that the funds realized are

utilized in the most effective and efficient manner. He emphasized further that resources are scarce and that all efforts should be made by educational administrators and planners to ensure optimal planning and utilization of funds. That is why Mgbodile (2014) viewed financial resource management as that management activity which is concerned with the planning and controlling of an organization financial resources. This means that financial resource management is concerned with decisions on how to produce, raise money, expand and give accounts of funds provided for the implementation of programmes of an organization or a school. Financial management is the fundamental element on which the success of any organization depends. Where the management is weak, success is hard to ascertain. No institution or school has ever succeeded in history without proper utilization of its resources. Poor management of finance results in financial misappropriation, embezzlement, diversion of finance for different projects and so on. Mgbodile (2014) summed up by enumerating some factors that lead to mismanagement of school funds to include: delay in release of funds to schools, diversion of funds to other sectors of the economy; lack of training or inadequate training of heads of educational institutions in issues of finance; financial clerks negligence in school finance matters; outright appointments by politicians of unqualified personnel to head schools; attitudes of form teachers in remitting fees collected to principals; and delay in payment of workers' salaries.

Kamaldeen et al. (2020) posited that school finance management is critical, because it allows school administrators to successfully fulfill teaching/learning objectives. According to Oluwaseun (2017), financial management in the educational sector, particularly in Nigeria is critical for improving educational quality and achieving the schools aims and goals. Making available the necessary school resources for increasing the quality, equity and excellence of education delivery can help to attain excellent education, hence, improve effective implementation of entrepreneurship education. Thus, sufficient finance must be provided in the universities for physical infrastructure, curriculum, and human resource availability, all in order to improve the quality of entrepreneurship education based on standard criteria (Uchendu et al., 2013). Revenue generation in schools is a way administrators demonstrate their financial management skills. Revenues in school are funds received by the schools which aids the management of school

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activities as well as supports teaching and learning process. Generating of revenue is an obligatory levy placed on individuals and stakeholders with the aim of raising funds for the school's numerous functions which include provision of entrepreneurship education for the students to enhance students' skills as well as promote job opportunities.

Lyons (2012) documented that learning of entrepreneurship education is a complex activity that supremely tests students' motivation, physical conditions, available resources, methods and skills of teaching, the school curricula and the administrators' ingenuity and expertise. He further stated that there is an explicit relationship between the physical characteristics and conditions of material resources, management effectiveness and efficiency and the outcomes. It must be noted that the implication of effective management of material resources for entrepreneurship education must of necessity take cognizance of the changes in teaching methods, the school grounds and environment, school curricula, designs and systems, ages and numerical strength of the children, personnel and expected outcomes; hence there is need for efficient financial management. Entrepreneurship training is seen as a leeway to unravel or reduce the unemployment state in the country with adequate theoretical, vocational and practical training. It has the mandate to equip the youth with functional knowledge and skills to build up their characters, attitudes and visions. Moreover, it has vital role in developing eco-system that enhances innovations (The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development [OECD], 2012).

Conclusion

Effective implementation and sustenance of entrepreneurship education depends largely on adequate provision of human and material resources in the schools. The quality and quantity of human resources is a serious pointer to the type of learning and skill the student are expected to acquire. However, the presence of human resources alone cannot make entrepreneurship education a success; relevant material resources are much needed to compliment the human resources. Therefore, the provision of both categories of resources in our universities in the right quality and quantity will make the required difference in terms of implementation

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Recommendation

It is recommended that;

1. All the stakeholders concerned with the implementation of entrepreneurship education should work relentlessly and collaboratively to ensure that the right thing is done in terms of proper provision of human and material resources for the programme.
2. There should be regular review of the existing material resources for entrepreneurship education in terms of relevance in line with the dynamics of change and time

REFERENCES

- Audretsch, D. B., Kuratko, D. F., & Link, A. N. (2016). Dynamic entrepreneurship and technology-based innovation. *Journal of Evolutionary Economics*, 26(2), 603–620. doi: 10.1007/s00191-016-0458-4.
- Bacigalupo, M., Kamyliis, P., Punie, Y., & Van den Brande, G. (2016). *EntreComp: the entrepreneurship competence framework*. Publication Office of the European Union). doi: 10.2791/593884.
- Duze, C. (2010) Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria: Funding Mechanisms. *An International Multi-Disciplinary Journal, Ethiopia*, 4(4), 236-245.
- Ejere, E. S. I., & Tende, S. B. A. (2012). Entrepreneurship and new venture creation. In E. Chuta (Ed.). *Small enterprises and entrepreneurship development*. Amalion Publishing.
- Ezeugbor, C. O., Onyali, L. C., & Okoye, F. O. (2018). Staff personnel administrative practices adopted by principals for promoting teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Research and Publications*, 2(1), 20-26.
- Falck, O., Gold, R., & Heblich, S. (2016). Lifting the iron curtain: school-age education and entrepreneurial intentions. *Journal of Economics and Geography*, 17(2), 1111–1148. doi: 10.1093/jeg/lbw026.
- Fang, R., Chi, L., & Chen, M. (2015). Bringing political skill into social networks: findings from a field study of entrepreneurs. *Journal of Management Studies*, 52(4), 175–212. doi: 10.1111/joms.12107.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). *National policy on education, (6th edition)*.

Received: 22 March, 2024

Revised: 2 April 2024

Final Accepted: 11 April 2024

- Hassan, D. A. (2013). Analysis of professional development practices for teachers in Pakistan: A comparative case study of public and private schools of Pakistan (Punjab). *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 3(4), 311-324.
- Ikoro, C. C. (2012). *Teamwork and teacher effectiveness in secondary schools in Ogba/Ndoni/Egbema Local Government Area of Rivers State* [Unpublished bachelor's Project]. University of Port Harcourt
- Kamaldeen, O. S., Oluyemisi, A. A., Busayo, O. A., Abdulrafiu, A., & Laro, I. Y. (2020). Human resource management and teachers' job performance in basic schools in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State. *African Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 13(2), 105-118.
- Kaur, K. (2012). *Staff development programmes*. www.slideshare.net/moneklrangura.
- Kelvin, S. A. (2016). *Relationship between motivation and teachers' job performance; factors that affect teachers' motivation and determine the motivational differences in public and private secondary schools in Tabora Municipality* [Unpublished master's dissertation]. Open University of Tanzania.
- Lyons (2012). *Do school facilities really impact a child's education? An introduction to the issues*. schoolfacilities.com/pdf/school.
- Mgbodile, T. O. (2014). *Fundamentals in educational administration and planning*. Enugu, Nigeria. Magnet Business Enterprise.
- OECD (2012), *Education at a Glance 2012: OECD Indicators*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/eag-2012-en>.
- Okonkwo, M. C. (2013). Teacher motivation: As a factor for school management. *ANSU Journal of Educational Research*, 1(1), 221-227.
- Oluwaseun, O. (2016). Effect of school variables on work performance in Calabar Municipal Area of Cross River State. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/effect-school-variables-student-academic-performance-Calabar-origin>.
- Onafadeji, A. O., Ogunyemi, F. F., & Alarape, B. A. (2017). Human resource management and employees performance in Federal University of Technology, Akure. *Journal of Business and Management*, 19(4), 95-104.
- Owan, V. J. (2018). *Personnel management functions: Implication for the school*. <https://goo.gl/KUQiiq>.

- Pfeffer, J. & Salancik, G. R. (1978). The External Control of Organizations: A Resource Dependence Perspective. Harper and Row.
- Uchendu, C. C., Ekanem, E. E., & Jonah. S. T. (2013). Resource maintenance for the provision of educational services in public and private secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 15-23.
- Uhl-Bien, M., & Arena, M. (2017). Complexity leadership: Enabling people and organizations for adaptability. *Organizational Dynamics*, 46(1), 9-20.
- UNESCO. (2020). United nation educational, scientific and cultural organization. Prioritize health and well-being now and when schools reopen. Retrieved from: <https://en.unesco.org/news/prioritize-health-and-well-being-now-and-when-schools-reopen>.

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